

Modelling the Effects of Selected Sociological and Psychological Factors on Secondary School Students' Achievement in Mathematics

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Abstract

The study explored the effects of two sociological constructs (classroom climate and parental involvement) and three psychological constructs (Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics task persistence) on senior secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics. The study was conducted at Nsukka Education Zone in Enugu State, Nigeria. A correlational survey design was employed in the study. Two research questions and two hypotheses led the study. The population of the study was 3037 Senior Secondary Two (SS2) Mathematics students from which a sample of 350 students was drawn using a multistage sampling procedure. Four adapted instruments; Students' Perceived Classroom Climate Questionnaire (SPCCQ), Students' Perceived Parental Involvement Questionnaire (SPPIQ), Students' Perceived Mathematics Self-Efficacy Questionnaire (SPMSQ), and Students' Perceived Mathematics Motivation Questionnaire (SPMMQ) and two researchers' developed instruments, namely, Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT), and Students' Perceived Mathematics Task Persistence Questionnaire were used for data collection. The estimate of internal consistence of the SPCCQ, SPPIQ, SPMSQ, and SPMMQ was done using Cronbach alpha which yielded reliability indices of 0.83, 0.86, 0.82, 0.91, and 0.78 respectively while the MAT yielded reliability index of 0.73 obtained through Kuder-Richardson (KR-20) formula. The collected data were analyzed using an R version 4.2.3 (R Core Team, 2022) package SEMinR version 2.2.1 (Ray et al., 2021). Research question one was answered using path coefficient (β) and effect size (f^2) while research question two was answered using multiple correlation (R). The two hypotheses were tested at 95% confidence interval. The findings indicated that the selected sociological and psychological constructs had both individual and joint positive significant effects on senior secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics. Based on these findings, recommendations were made.

Introduction

Many factors, of course affect students' achievement in Mathematics. Hence, understanding the interrelationships among these factors is vital to improve students' learning of Mathematics. While studies have shown that factors that affect learning outcomes include student factors, school factors, and home factors, there seems to be scarcity of studies that have examined the composite effects and mediational roles of some of these factors on students' achievement in Mathematics. These factors may also be classified as sociological and psychological factors. Hence, the need to model the effects of two sociological factors (classroom climate, parental involvement) and three psychological factors (Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics persistence) on secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics.

Mathematics is an essential subject for students all over the world. Mathematics is taught, not only at secondary school level, but also spans through primary to tertiary education. Historically, Mathematics was designed to enable mankind tackle computational challenges emanated from complexity in keeping records of daily activities of farmers. For instance, as the number of livestock and farm produce was increasing, man moved away from the use of tallies, stones, and counters in counting to development and of number system in keeping records. Presently, Mathematics is no longer restricted to number and numeration, but has included algebra, geometry, statistics, trigonometry, among others.

The applications of Mathematics have permeated almost every field of study, including engineering, medicine, banking and finance, education, economics, pharmacology, and host of others. The wide applications of Mathematical knowledge could be the reason a good grade obtained in School Certificate Mathematics Examinations is considered as one of the criteria for gaining admission into tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Giving the growing demand for students to obtain good grades in Mathematics, it is therefore expected that students should match this demand with good achievement in the subject.

However, despite the need for good academic achievement in Mathematics, performance of secondary school students in the subject does not reflect the importance attached to the subject. For instance, evidences abound of students' learning difficulties in every branch of Mathematics (Ogbu&Anyaegebu, 2021). Persistent annual students' under performance in Mathematics has been reported in the National Examination Council (NECO), and the West African Examination Council (WAEC), National Examination Council (NECO) in Nigeria (Ahumaraeze&Ekwueme, 2019). The reoccurring under performance of secondary school Mathematics students could be the reason it is said that the teaching and learning of Mathematics is not meeting the national development demand of Nigeria (Unodaku&Nankpa, 2020). Of course, compared to other subjects, student' achievement in Mathematics is increasingly discouraging (Ehiwario, et al., 2020; Charles-Organ &Zalmon, 2020; Popoola& Ajani, 2011). Unfortunately, poor achievement of students in Mathematics is not without negative impacts.

The persistent poor achievement of student in Mathematics has dire consequences. For instance, many students could miss admission opportunities into tertiary institutions because of their inability to obtain the minimum requirement of at least a credit pass in WAEC or NECO Mathematics for admission into tertiary institutions. This situation could lead to depression and frustration after several attempts to get a credit pass in Mathematics without positive result. The indirect effects include that some students could easily drop out, and may not contribute meaningfully for the development of the society. Again, with high incidence of insecurity, and other anti-social activities, such as cultism, prostitution, banditry, kidnapping, and boko-haram, allowing poor achievement to persist and to continue denying some students admission in tertiary institution does not spell good for Nigeria that is technological dependent nation. Hence, efforts to urgently boost students' achievement in Mathematics should be acknowledged. Interestingly, in the efforts to address students' poor achievement in Mathematics, number of researchers have identified some factors that could account for students' learning of Mathematics (Ogini, 2020; Enu, Angyman, &Nkum, 2015; Chaman, Bestwick, &Callingham, 2014; Al-Agili, Mamat, &Maad, 2012). However, there is still gap in the knowledge regarding the joint effects and mediational effects of some of these factors on students' academic achievement, hence a need for more studies in this area. Most of the factors that could affect academic achievement could be categorized into sociological and psychological factors. Sociological and psychological factors are constructs that cannot be measured directly but through the use of questionnaire items.

Psychological constructs examined in this study include students' motivation to learn Mathematics, self-efficacy in Mathematics, and Mathematics task persistence. Self-efficacy is defined as the students' judgment about their ability to perform a particular activity (Siegle&McCoach, 2007). It also describes individual confidence in their task accomplishment ability (Liu &Koirala, 2009). It is expected of the students to develop self-efficacy in tasks related to learning various school subjects such as Mathematics. In this paper, students' Mathematics self-efficacy is conceptualized as the students' confidence in performing or solving Mathematics tasks.

Literature Review

Effect of Mathematics Self-efficacy on Academic Achievement in Mathematics

The effect of self-efficacy in teaching and learning episodes seems to be positive. Many observations seem to agree that self-efficacy is a powerful construct in determining learning outcomes. For instance, low Mathematics self-efficacy is said to be associated with poor interest in Mathematics (Oldham, 2018). Self-efficacy was also found to significantly influence students' achievement in Mathematics (Negara, Nurlaelan, Wahyudin, Herman, &Tamur, 2020; Hoyet, Shateri, &Amini, 2020). Researchers, although have noted the significant influence of self-efficacy on students' academic achievement, there is little or no knowledge of the joint effect of self-efficacy and other constructs, such as motivation on students' achievement in Mathematics.

Effect of Mathematics Motivation on Academic Achievement in Mathematics

There are documented evidences of effect motivation on students' learning. For instance, motivation is regarded as one of the factors that determines the level of goal accomplishment. Children's motivation predicts their motivation in later life (Broussard & Garrison, 2004). Combination of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation leads to increase in the students' interest, engagement, creativity, persistence, and academic achievement (Lens & Tsuzuki, 2005; Um, 2008). Secondary school students with high motivation also show higher achievement in Mathematics as compare to students' with low motivation (Tella, 2007). High grade motivation has been recognised as a significant predictor of Philippines university students' Mathematics performance (Villa & Sebastian, 2021). Similarly, Sartawi, Alsawie, Dodeen, Tibi, and Alghazo (2012) found that motivation was a significant factor in students' Mathematics achievement in United Arab Emirate. Motivational factors play significant roles in students' achievement in Mathematics (Meshack, 2013). Intrinsic motivation was found to have a positive association with students' Mathematics achievement (Tran & Nguyen, 2021). Contrarily, it is reported that intrinsic motivation has no significant influence on Canadian school-aged children's achievement in Mathematics (Garon-Carrier et al., 2016). The controversial findings on the effect Mathematics motivation on students' achievement in Mathematics calls for more studies to better gain insight on the effect motivation on performance of students in Mathematics. Hence, this gap in knowledge necessitate this present study. More so, the joint effect of motivation and other psychological and sociological variables on students' achievement in Mathematics needs to be brought to limelight. Another important construct needed for effective learning is academic task persistence.

Effect of Mathematics Persistence on Academic Achievement in Mathematics

Evidence shows that highly persistent students obtained high academic achievement (Verma, 2016). Considering the limited studies and information on the effect of Mathematics task persistence on the Mathematics performance of elementary school students, it becomes pertinent to model the effect of Mathematics task persistence on senior secondary school students' achievement in the subject. This study is poised to fill this gap. Above all, the joint effect of Mathematics task persistence on students' achievement in Mathematics was also determined.

Effect of Classroom Climate on Academic Achievement in Mathematics

Evidence abounds of the links between students' performance and classroom climate in different subjects in different locations. For example, classroom climate plays a significant role in Social Studies students' academic performance (Ekpo, Akpan, Essien, & Omo-Obot, 2009). Classroom climate is also a significant predictor of students' achievement in KSCE examination in Kenya (Okendo, Christopher, & Janifer, 2014). The theory that a positive classroom climate leads to greater academic engagement which in turn leads to academic achievement has been confirmed (Konold, Cornell, Jia, & Malone, 2018). Contrarily, Tharani and Geetha (2017) concluded that among high school students, the relationship between their classroom climate and academic performance was not significant. Oni (2020) also noted that students' performance in Mathematics was not significantly determined by classroom climate. From the literature review, more research is needed to understand the exact link between classroom climate and students' achievement in Mathematics. It is pointed out that how school climate is related to students' academic outcomes is a question that needs an answer (Konold et al., 2018). Therefore, it is worthy to explore the joint effect of classroom climate, parental involvement, among others, on the performance of students in Mathematics.

Effect of Parental Involvement on Academic Achievement in Mathematics

Parental involvement influence both the cognitive abilities and affective behaviour of learners. For example, children whose parents show greater parental involvement show high achievement motivation (Lemmar, 2007). Similarly, when the parents show greater involvement, the students display greater readiness and persistence to learn (Sapungan&Sapungan, 2014). Greater academic achievement is strongly related to parental involvement (Emeagwali, 2009; Epstein, 2009). It is pointed out that parental involvement makes the parents to be more comfortable with and have trust in the school system (Llama & Tuazan, 2016). Parental involvement in students' learning is related with high achievement of students in education (Topor, Keane, Shelton, & Calkins, 2010). Some dimension of parental involvement such as parental expectation, parents-child discussion, and parental expectation have significant relationship with students' achievement in Mathematics (Huang, Huang, Li, & Zhang, 2021; Myers, 2021). Similarly, students that have family members that are highly involved in students' learning outperform their counterparts that have low involved parents in Mathematics (Martinez, 2021).

While some researchers have found positive and significant effect of classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics task persistence on students' academic

achievement whereas, some researchers reported no significant effect. More worrisomely, there is no evidence of the joint effect of classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics task persistence on Mathematics performance of secondary school students. This gap in knowledge demands that a research in this area, hence, the need for the present study.

Theoretical Background and Hypotheses Development

Figure 1: Hypothesized Model for the Study (Source authors)

Key: CC = Classroom Climate, PI = Parental Involvement; SE= Mathematics Self-efficacy; MM= Mathematics Motivation MP= Mathematics Persistence, AM= Achievement in Mathematics

The paths for the hypothesized, in Figure 1 were specified based on empirical evidences and theories. The path, a, represents the influence of CC on AM. This is in line with the observation that classroom climate explains students' Mathematics achievement (Maxwell, Reynolds, Lee, Subasic, & Bromhead, 2017). The path, b, represents the influence of CC on MP. The path is specified in the model considering the fact that learning environment characteristics are significantly related to students' persistence in English Language (Mutlu&Yildirim, 2019) and that learning environment significantly predict postgraduate students' persistence to complete their programs (Ivankova& Stick, 2007). The path, c, represents the influence of CC on MM. The reason for considering the path is that negative classroom climate is associated with decrease in students' motivation (Kormos&Luckoczky as cited in Heitzmann, 2009). Therefore, high classroom climate implies high motivation. The path, d, represents the influence of CC on SE. This path is included in model based on the fact that learning environment is significantly related to students' self-efficacy beliefs in learning English Language (Doggol, 2019). Therefore, classroom climate could as well influence students' learning in Mathematics.

The influence of parental involvement on Mathematics achievement was specified based on empirical evidence. For instance, significant influence of parental involvement on Mathematics achievement has been observed (Lara & Saracosti, 2019). Hence the reason for the path, e, which reflects the influence of PI on AM. It has also been noted that a strength-based parenting and parental support influence students' perseverance and persistence in academic work (Grant, 2020; Waters, Loton, & Jach, 2018). Therefore, the researcher considered the path, f, which implies the influence of PI on MP. Students' perception of parental involvement predicts secondary school students' motivation (Nunez, Regueiro, Suarez, Pineiro, Rodicio, & Valle, 2019). This is specified by the path, g, which denotes the influence of PI on MM. Students' learning motivation is influenced strongly by many factors which include: classroom environment (Akomolafe&Adesua, 2015; Anderson, et al., 2004) and parental involvement (Varghese & Devi, 2019; Pavalache-IIie&Tirdia, 2015). Similarly, parental involvement is described as a strong factor that predicts the Mathematics self-efficacy of the students (Fan & Williams, 2010). This is shown in the path, h, which specifies the influence of PI on SE.

Furthermore, the path linking Mathematics self-efficacy and students' achievement was specified based on theory and empirical evidence. Mathematics self-efficacy has been identified as a strong influential factor in

college students' Mathematics achievement (Taheri-Kharamah, Sharififard, Asayesh, Sepahvand, & Hoseini, 2018). This relationship is reflected by path, i, which implies the influence of SE on AM. More so, the relationship between self-efficacy beliefs and students' persistence has been described as positive and strong (Schnell et al. as cited in Dullas, 2018). Hence the researcher hypothesized that SE has an influence on MP which is shown by the path, j. Mathematics self-efficacy beliefs have been described as a key factor contributing to students' academic motivation (Herges et al., 2017). The path, k, depicts the influence of SE on MM. This implies that there is a hypothesized influence of self-efficacy on motivation.

Motivation could influence academic achievement, hence, the reason for the path from students' perceived Mathematics Motivation students' achievement in Mathematics, according to Herges et al., (2017) is significantly related to student's academic achievement. This relationship is shown in the model by the path, l, which entails that MM influences AM. Motivation has been recognized as a critical component in adult online learners' persistence (Lucey, 2018). Hence secondary school students' Mathematics motivation is hypothesized to influence students' Mathematics persistence. This is shown by the path, m, which represents the influence of MM on MP. Finally, the Mathematics persistence of Grade 6 students is a significant predictor of Mathematics problem-solving of the students (Stoll, 2015). Consequently, Mathematics persistence may likely predict Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in Nigeria. The path, m, shows the influence of MP on AM.

Hypotheses

- H₀₁:** The individual effect of classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics task persistence on senior secondary school performance of students in Mathematics is not statistically significant.
- H₀₂:** The composite effect of classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics task persistence on senior secondary school performance of students in Mathematics is not statistically significant.

Methods

A correlational research approach was utilized in this study. A correlational research is appropriate when a researcher intends to ascertain the relationship between or among variables (Creswell, 2012). The design was considered suitable for the present study as the relationship between the sociological and psychological and students' academic achievement in Mathematics was determined. The study was conducted at Nsukka Education Zone in Enugu State Niger. The zone is made up of three Local Government Areas-Nsukka, Uzo-Uwani, and Igbo-Etiti, of which a total of 62 public secondary schools were distributed. A total of 3037 Senior Secondary Two (SS2) students constituted the population. A sample size of 350 which was above the minimum recommended sample size of 150 (Civelek, 2018) and 200 (Celik&Yalmaz, 2013) was used in the study. The sample size was selected using a multi-stage sampling approach which involved sampling schools from the Local Government Area and sampling students from the intact classes. Six research data collection tools were used. The tools comprised Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) developed by the researchers, the Students' Perceived Classroom Climate Questionnaire (SPCCQ) adapted from (Lopez, et al., 2019), the Students' Perceived Parental Involvement Questionnaire (SPPIQ), the Students' Perceived Mathematics Self-efficacy Questionnaire (SPMSQ) adapted from (Oldham, 2018), Students' Perceived Mathematics Motivation Questionnaire (SPMMQ) adapted from (Butler, 2016), and Students' Perceived Mathematics Task Persistence Questionnaire (SPMTPQ) developed by the researchers. The MAT was a 25-item multiple-choice questions developed using a table of specification designed by the researchers. Each item of the MAT has four options, lettered A to D from which the students select one option. The SPCCQ, SPPIQ, SPMMQ, and SPMTP have 8, 9, 8, 9, and 6 items respectively, and were rated using a 7-point Likert type scale which ranged from *Not True of Me at all (1 point) to very true of me (7 points)*.

For the face validation of the instruments, three experts one in Education Psychology, one in Educational Measurement and Evaluation, and on Education Mathematics, all from the Faculty of Education University of Nigeria Nsukka, validated the research instruments. The construct validity of the SPCCQ, SPPIQ, SPMMQ, and SPMTP was determined after responses obtained from 200 trial-tested respondents (not the actual respondents in the study) were subjected to confirmatory factor analysis. The following fit statistics: Ratio of Chi-square and the degree of freedom (χ^2/df) the acceptable values need to be ≤ 5.00 , Comparative Fit Index (CFI) the acceptable values need to be ≥ 0.90 , Tucker-Lewis Index (TFI), the acceptable values need to be ≥ 0.90 , Root Mean Square Residual (RMSR), the values need to be ≤ 0.05 , Standard Root Mean Square Residual (SRMSR), the values need to be ≤ 0.05 (Rivera-Lacia, 2019) were evaluated and found to be within the acceptable range for the hypothesized models. The estimate of the internal consistency of the SPCCQ, SPPIQ, SPMMQ, and

SPMTP obtained using Cronbach alpha show reliability indices of 0.83, 0.86, 0.82, 0.91, and 0.78 respectively. The estimate of the internal consistence of the MAT was done using Kuder-Richardson (KR-20) which showed a reliability index of 0.73. After screening the collected data, the data were subjected to partial least structural equation modelling analysis using R version 4.2.3 (R Core Team, 2022) while structural parameters were estimated using SEMinR version 2.2.1(Ray et al., 2021) and plspm version 0.4.9 (Sanchez &Trinchera, 2012) packages. Research question one was answered using effect size where the interpretations of effect size were as follows: 0-0.10 weak effect, 0.21-0.50 modest effect, 0.51-1.00 moderate effect, and above 1.00 strong effect (Cohen &Manion, 2007). Research question two was answered using the coefficient of determination, R^2 . For interpretation, R^2 values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 were considered substantial, moderate, and weak (Hair et al., 2022).The two null hypotheses were tested at 95% confidence intervals using a bootstrapping procedure. The decision rule was to reject the null hypotheses if 95% confidence intervals contain zero.

Results

Evaluation of Measurement Model

Table 1: Assessment of Convergent Validity of the Trimmed Measurement Model

Latent Variables	Items (Indicators)	Loading	Alpha	rhoC	AVE
Classroom Climate (CC)	CLASS1	0.668	0.85	0.86	0.53
	CLASS5	0.721			
	CLASS6	0.676			
	CLASS7	0.774			
	CLASS8	0.806			
	Parental Involvement (PP)				
Mathematics Self-Efficacy (SE)	PAREN3	0.837	0.91	0.91	0.61
	PAREN4	0.794			
	PAREN5	0.853			
	PAREN6	0.654			
	PAREN9	0.654			
Mathematics Motivation (MM)	SELF2	0.792	0.90	0.91	0.55
	SELF3	0.773			
	SELF4	0.768			
	SELF5	0.815			
	SELF6	0.785			
	SELF7	0.770			
Mathematics Persistence (MP)	MOTI1	0.819	0.80	0.80	0.50
	MOTI2	0.831			
	MOTI3	0.840			
	MOTI5	0.675			
	MOTI6	0.640			
	MOTI7	0.644			
Mathematics Persistence (MP)	MOTI8	0.720	0.80	0.80	0.50
	MOTI9	0.709			
	PERSI1	0.714			
	PERSI2	0.697			
Mathematics Persistence (MP)	PERSI5	0.698	0.80	0.80	0.50
	PERSI6	0.728			

Table 1 shows the retained indicators for the exogenous and endogenous variables. From the Table 1, the purified indicator loadings for the students' Classroom Climate (CC) ranged from 0.676 to 0.806, the indicator loadings for students parental involvement (PI) ranged from 0.654 to 0.897, the indicator loadings for students' Mathematics Self-efficacy (SE) ranged from 0.770 to 0.815, the indicator loadings for students Mathematics Motivation (MM) ranged from 0.640 to 0.840, while the indicator loadings for students' Mathematics Persistence (MP) ranged from 0.697 to 0.728. All the indicator loadings were within the acceptable range. The assessment of the consistency reliability shows that all the indicators were reliable as they had Cronbach's alpha and rhoC values ranging from 0.85 to 0.92. There was evidence of convergent validity of all the constructs as the AVE values for the constructs ranged from 0.53 to 0.61 which is above the minimum recommended value of 0.50. The discriminant validity was also assessed after removing unreliable items. This implies that the retain items are the best measures of the psychological and sociological constructs.

Table 2: Assessment of Discriminant validity of the Trimmed Model using HTMT

Paths	HTMT	Bootstrap Mean	Bootstrap SD	t	2.5% CI	97.5% CI	Decision
CC -> PI	0.45	0.45	0.07	6.46	0.31	0.59	S
CC -> SE	0.39	0.41	0.06	6.03	0.29	0.53	S
CC -> MM	0.42	0.42	0.07	6.15	0.29	0.56	S
CC -> MP	0.36	0.37	0.07	5.37	0.24	0.49	S
CC -> AM	0.60	0.59	0.06	10.10	0.47	0.70	S
PI -> SE	0.65	0.66	0.05	11.92	0.55	0.76	S
PI -> MM	0.85	0.84	0.04	20.65	0.76	0.92	S
PI -> MP	0.64	0.64	0.05	14.13	0.55	0.73	S
PI -> AM	0.85	0.85	0.03	32.21	0.80	0.90	S
SE -> MM	0.76	0.77	0.05	16.39	0.68	0.85	S
SE -> MP	0.54	0.54	0.06	9.32	0.43	0.65	S
SE -> AM	0.81	0.81	0.03	28.36	0.75	0.86	S
MM -> MP	0.61	0.61	0.04	13.82	0.52	0.70	S
MM -> AM	0.84	0.84	0.02	34.20	0.79	0.88	S
MP -> AM	0.68	0.68	0.04	18.57	0.61	0.74	S

Table 2 shows the indicator loadings, the bootstrap mean values, the bootstrap standard deviation values, the t-statistic values, and the lower and upper percentile of the 95% bootstrap confidence interval values. The results on Table 5 shows that the values of the heterotrait–monotrait (HTMT) Ratio ranged from 0.36 to 0.85. All the HTMT values were within the acceptable value of ≤ 0.90 . HTMT value above 0.90 suggests the presence of discriminant validity problem. Bootstrap confidence interval further suggested that all the HTMT values are significant different from the benchmark value of 0.90. Thus, discriminant validity is not an issue in the trimmed model. This implies that the indicators were actually measuring the constructs they represent and nothing else.

Hypothesis One: The individual effect of classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics task persistence to senior secondary school performance of students in Mathematics is not statistically significant.

Table 3: Path Coefficients, Bootstrap Mean, Bootstrap Standard Deviation, t-Stat, and Upper and Lower 95% Bootstrapped Confidence Interval

Relation	Original Est.	Bootstrap Mean	Bootstrap SD	t Stat.	2.5% CI	97.5% CI	Remark
CC -> MA	0.237	0.240	0.029	8.237	0.183	0.295	Sig.
PI -> MA	0.212	0.212	0.063	3.385	0.082	0.318	Sig.
MSE -> MA	0.264	0.267	0.039	6.715	0.196	0.344	Sig.
MM -> MA	0.211	0.207	0.067	3.151	0.076	0.320	Sig.
MTP -> MA	0.188	0.187	0.039	4.826	0.107	0.260	Sig.

Table 3 shows the path coefficients (original), the bootstrap mean values, the bootstrap standard deviation values, t-stat. values, and the lower and upper percentile of the 95% bootstrap confidence interval values. The effect of classroom climate (CC) on the performance of students in Mathematics was significant (CC -> MA,

$\beta=0.237$, $t=8.237$, $[0.183; 0.295]$). Similarly, students' perceived parental involvement had significant effects on students' academic achievement in Mathematics (PI \rightarrow MA, $\beta=0.212$, $t=3.385$, $[0.082; 0.318]$). Furthermore, students' Mathematics self-efficacy belief (MSE) had significant effect on the performance of students in Mathematics (SE \rightarrow MA, $\beta=0.264$, $t=6.715$, $[0.196; 0.344]$). Students' perceived Mathematics motivation (MM) and students' Mathematics task persistence had significant effects on performance of students in Mathematics (MM \rightarrow MA, $\beta=0.211$, $t=3.151$, $[0.076, 0.320]$; MTP \rightarrow MA, $\beta=0.188$, $t=4.826$, $[0.107; 0.260]$).

Hypothesis Two: The composite effect of classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics task-persistence to senior secondary school performance of students in Mathematics is not statistically significant.

Table 4: Multiple Correlation Coefficient (R) Coefficient of Determination (R^2), Mean Boot, T-Stat, and Upper and Lower 95% Bootstrapped Confidence Interval Analysis for Testing of Significant of R^2 Values

	R	R^2	Mean.Boot	Std.Error	t-Stat.	perc.025	perc.975	Remarks
MA	0.86	0.742	0.747	0.029	25.586	0.689	0.805	Sig.

Table 4 shows that there was a very strong positive composite effect of students' perceived classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics task persistence on senior secondary school performance of students in Mathematics $R=0.86$, $R^2 = 0.72$, $t=25.59$, 95% CI=[0.689-0.805]. In other words, the regression model, $MA=CC*0.24+PI*0.21+MSE*0.26+MM*0.21+MTP*0.81+constant$ is a significant predictor senior secondary school performance of students in Mathematics. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that the composite effects of classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics persistence on performance of students in Mathematics is not statistically significant was rejected.

Figure 2: The Validated Model (Source Authors)

Note:

*=Significant, ns = Not Significant; CC=Classroom Climate, PI=Parental Involvement, SE=Mathematics Self-efficacy, Mathematics Motivation, MP=Mathematics Persistence, AM= Achievement in Mathematics

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that the individual effects of classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics task persistence on the performance of students in Mathematics were all significant. These findings are not surprising given that when a teacher creates a conducive learning environment where by student-student interaction and teacher-student interaction are properly harnessed, students tend to engage more in learning. This could account for the effect of classroom climate on the performance of students in Mathematics The findings are in agreement with (Konold, Cornell, Jia, & Malone, 2018) who confirmed a theory that relates classroom climate and students' academic

achievement. The findings of the study also corroborated (Okendo, Christopher, & Janifer, 2014) who discovered that classroom climate was a significant predictor of students' achievement in KSCE examination in Kenya. However, the findings disagreed with (Oni, 2020; Tharanie and Geetha, 2017) who discovered that classroom climate was not a significant factor on students' academic achievement.

Again, when the parents or guardians complement the effort of the school in students' learning by providing the needed learning materials and assisting students with academic-related tasks at home, the students could often reciprocate their parents' effort through more academic engagement. The findings support (Huang, Huang, Li, & Zhang, 2021; Myers, 2021) who found that some dimensions of parental involvement such as parental expectation, and parents-child discussion, have a significant relationship with the performance of students in Mathematics. It also aligns with (Marinez, 2021) who reported that students who have family members who are highly involved in the students' learning outperform their counterparts who have low-involved parents in Mathematics.

The idea that students who perceive their confidence in Mathematics to be high could demonstrate more academic achievement could account for the effect of self-efficacy and senior secondary school performance of students in Mathematics. The study concurred with (Oldham, 2018) that low Mathematics self-efficacy is associated with poor interest in Mathematics. More so the study is in line with (Negara, Nurlaelan, Wahyudin, Herman, & Tamur, 2020; Hoyet, Shateri, & Amini, 2020) who found that self-efficacy significantly influenced the performance of students in Mathematics.

More students who learn Mathematics because they have realized the need to get good grades in Mathematics might be some of the major reasons that drive the relationship between Mathematics motivation and achievement in Mathematics. The findings reaffirm (Sartawi, Alsawie, Dodeen, Tibi, & Alghazo, 2012; Tella, 2007) who reported that secondary school students with high motivation also show higher achievement in Mathematics as compared to students with low motivation. Similarly, the findings support (Villa & Sebastian, 2021) who demonstrated that high achievement motivation was a significant predictor of Philippines university performance of students in Mathematics. Similarly, found that motivation was a significant factor in students' Mathematics achievement in the United Arab Emirates.

The positive significant effect of Mathematics task persistence on students' academic achievement demonstrated the importance of persistence in learning. Furthermore, Mathematics task persistence entails that students do not give up easily when attempting to solve difficult Mathematics tasks, hence the students' ability to keep solving until the solutions to difficult tasks could be the reason behind the significant effect of Mathematics task persistence and senior secondary school performance of students in Mathematics. The findings are in agreement with those (Verma, 2016) found that highly persistent students obtained high academic achievement.

The findings of the study also showed that the joint effect of classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics task persistence on the performance of students in Mathematics were all significant. These findings are not also surprising as all these factors could interact and influence the performance of students in Mathematics. For instance, in a friendly classroom and academic-oriented homes, students tend to be motivated both intrinsically and extrinsically, hence their learning confidence could be enhanced resulting in high persistence. This culminates in higher academic achievement in Mathematics.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that students' classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics persistence play significant roles in secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics. Mathematics self-efficacy and Mathematics persistence play significant mediational roles in transmitting the effects of classroom climate and parental involvement to students' achievement in Mathematics. And that the composite effects of these selected psychological and sociological variables for this study are also significant determinant of secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the findings of this study, the following educational implications of the findings are highlighted as they relate to the teacher, students, education authorities, curriculum developers, and the Mathematics textbook. The findings of this study have provided empirical evidence on the predictive model that relates students' classroom climate, parental involvement, Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics persistence to secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics. The findings have demonstrated that classroom climate influenced students' achievement in Mathematics. The

implication of this finding to Mathematics teachers is that the classroom climates the teacher creates is one of the key factors that determines students' achievement in Mathematics. Hence the teachers could see the need to strive to create positive classroom climate that would improve students' Mathematics self-efficacy, Mathematics motivation, and Mathematics persistence to learn. Since the self-efficacy, motivation, and persistence play significant roles transmitting the effect of classroom climate to students' achievement in Mathematics, the teachers' could in the course of teaching, see the need to motivate the students, especially those with low self-efficacy and low persistence in solving Mathematics to overcome their weaknesses. Furthermore, the findings of the study imply that there is the need for Mathematics teachers to improve on their classroom management through participation in workshops, conferences, and seminars.

For the parents, the findings of this study implies that parents have the chance to contribute to students learning. It implies that the era whereby the parents expect the teachers to do all the teaching work has gone. In other words, parental involvement is as important as teachers' support when it comes to students' achievement in Mathematics. Hence, parents/guardians have the responsibility to monitor what the children learn at home.

For the students, the findings of this study implies that the students have hope of increased achievement in Mathematics, if the teachers create conducive classroom climate and the parents actively involved in students' learning. More so, the findings of this study could make the students to see need help in maintaining good classroom climate and also initiate parental involvement in students' education. The students could be easily motivated, and also show high self-efficacy and persistent in solving Mathematics. All this could in turn improve students' achievement in Mathematics. With increased parental involvement, teachers' creation of good classroom climate, students' motivation, and demonstration of high Mathematics self-efficacy and Mathematics persistence, the unwarranted phobia for Mathematics and the concomitant poor achievement in the subjects will be kept at bay. Consequently, general poor achievement in Mathematics external examinations conducted by WAEC and NECO will improve. This would result in the increase in the number of students admitted in the tertiary institution to study sciences and science related courses.

Finally, the findings of this study have implications for education policy and decision makers. Since the validated predictive model showed that classroom climate and parental involvement affect students' achievement in Mathematics, it becomes the responsibility of the policy and decision makers to explore means to ensure that students' learn Mathematics in conducive classroom climate. Education authorities are now in the position to provide spacious classrooms with adequate ventilation, light, and the needed instructional materials. More so, the education authorities have the responsibility to sensitize the parents on the need for the parents to compliment the efforts of the teachers by becoming actively involved in students' education.

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